

BRICS+ Industrial Development and Transformative Leapfrogging

Giovana Silva Santiago

Abstract

With the emergence of new technologies, the world has found itself searching for new ways of leading a more sustainable future. In 2021, BRICS created the Partnership for the New Industrial Revolution to identify common interests, challenges and opportunities for emerging economies. Considering that, this paper aims to discuss how the transformative leapfrogging perspective is an alternative path for industrial development through the foment of new markets and agendas, for latecomers industries.

Keywords: Transformative leapfrogging; Artificial Intelligence; Industrial Growth; BRICS

Introduction

With the emergence of new technologies and world races to develop them going on the most extreme grounds, artificial intelligence as a general-purpose technology of civilizational scale presents a question to the running countries: how can those considered industrial latecomers, specifically BRICS+ countries, use artificial intelligence to bypass altogether the current industrialization panorama? As a group with significant demographic scale, institutional goals in progress and heterogeneity amongst its members, there is the ambition to develop more inside the sector and to become global leaders not only for the Global South, but to the rest of the world as well.

Focused on an exploratory character, this paper focuses on identifying the conditions where AI leapfrogging presents itself as a conditional yet viable developmental strategy. The methodology draws on bibliography review and its guidelines established by Baumeister and Leary (1997) and Snyder (2019), focusing on BRICS+ official declarations, statements and institutional frameworks. With such a combination, this paper aims to discuss, even if primarily on the potential that BRICS+ countries hold inside the existing field and its part on the building of something new.

BRICS+ and the industrial agenda

Despite acting as a unified voice for the Global South in international forums, the BRICS+ group has never been exactly a homogeneous industrial entity. The membership ranges from China, the world's largest manufacturer and increasingly dominant force, to members with embryonic industrial bases who are shaped by commodity dependency, as discussed by structuralist economists as the central obstacle to peripheral development (Prebisch, 1950). It is within such a landscape that BRICS summits have attempted to construct a common framework capable of accommodating different backgrounds, capabilities and developmental priorities of members separated by industrial divergence.

However, these efforts to coordinate a broader framework and cooperation of entities inside BRICS, still don't seem to be enough to minimize its members' very heterogeneous internal panorama of industrialization. Due to their internal government policies, investment areas and approaches to the manufacturing reality, BRICS countries are now facing industrialization gaps, with China taking a different route and strengthening its role as an industrial leader (Naudé, Szirmai and Lavopa, 2013). According to Santiago (2020), a common factor between BRICS countries is the internal articulation between industrial policies, innovation and education, in order to boost productive capability, while also alternating the degrees of political intervention, going from implementing import substitutions measures in government-centred industrial periods, to more liberal approaches inspired by the Washington Consensus, like the privatization of national companies and industrial policies that rule in favor of strategic sectors.

Established in 2021, the BRICS Partnership on the New Industrial Revolution (PartNIR) became the first dedicated framework inside BRICS for industrial transformation cooperation, covering digital manufacturing, innovation and dialogue perspectives for all the members and companies who joined the initiative (BRICS, 2025). One year later, the Beijing Declaration showed the group's commitment to the translation of the partnership's vision into real actions, promoting the expansion of the training programmes between the involved entities inside the BRICS industrial agenda, such as the BRICS Centre for Industrial Competences, the BRICS PartNIR Innovation Centre (BPIC) and the BRICS Start-up Events (BRICS, 2022).

On a general perspective, BRICS countries latest industrial initiatives revolve around similar aspects with PartNIR playing an important role in setting the common grounds of a future general agenda for the group. The segment is coordinated by the BRICS countries ministries related to industry, development, services and entrepreneurship, with the discussions being about the industrial performances of artificial intelligence, manufacturing and applied robotics, investments regarding small and medium companies, while also articulating the integration of bioindustry and circular economy (BRICS, 2025).

According to Lee and Malerba (2017), developing countries who seek to upgrade to more advanced industrial levels, must be able to perform with readiness during the windows of opportunities, moments generated by technological discontinuities, market transitions or shifts within the dominant paradigm and open space for latecomers to either enter the systems in some sort of way or to advance other inside industrial systems. However, this mentality of catching-up with others may futurely turn into positive returns for the latecomers in question, with a gradual pay-off of such investments, but at the cost of interdependency ties with existing markets mainstream products, values and views, hardly grasping the possibility of the creation of an alternative reality.

Opposing this perspective, Lee (2024) argues that such a method is not a sufficient development. Countries bet on spending money to develop technologies to already solidified markets, arriving late to the competition that has already solidified its shares and revenue dividends. Lee's alternative then, is for such countries to do a detour from the tradition and to choose for a path inside emerging paradigms where rules of competition and advantages are still being built. Whitfield and Wuttke (2025), point that structural barriers inside the catching up method are becoming less sustainable due to their constant reconstructions by leading economies, with paradigm-shifting technologies representing better walkaways to those from peripheral status.

Steinmuller (2001) and Fong (2009), discuss that the absence of legacy systems can function as a productive space where when a new technology emerges, a new technological generation does as well, setting the steps for its development before the intermediate infrastructure has been solidified. With BRICS+, such conditions are uneven but present, due to members with nascent manufacturing bases being better positioned than more

industrialized ones to deploy AI-integrated production without the transition costs that burden established economies. For BRICS+ as a group, such tension is the central political income challenge that PartNIT, the BRICS Centre for Industrial Competences, and the 2025 AI Declaration must navigate if the group's industrial ambitions are to translate into equitable and sovereign development.

AI leapfrogging and alternatives for the Global South

By the end of the 2025 BRICS Summit, the traditional leaders' statement gained a full extension regarding one of the most important topics of the 2020s: artificial intelligence (AI) and its governance. Despite being present in previous documents from the group, for the first time ever since the rising of discussions towards AI within BRICS+ countries, the subject was released in a standalone, high-level declaration, showcasing to the international system that not only it became a new part of the BRICS+ agenda, but it also takes part as one of its pillars regarding their fight towards a more plural development agenda. The document, entitled as the "BRICS Leaders Statement on the Global Governance of Artificial Intelligence", shows that for the countries within the group, AI governance is seen as a potential tool for mitigating risks and potential threats that may come from the non-regulation of such technology (BRICS, 2025).

The declaration does not merely endorse AI as a tool of economic modernization, but it also positions governance itself as a developmental instrument, reflecting a distinctly Global South reading of the potentials of the technology. Where the European Union's AI Act from 2024 approaches regulation primarily through the lens of risk mitigation and fundamental rights, the BRICS+ declaration foregrounds sovereignty, inclusivity, and the equitable distribution of AI's benefits across nations at different stages of development (BRICS, 2025). Roberts (2021), argues that the central dispute in global AI governance is focused on different state models and the values encoded into the infrastructure of the next industrial era.

For Couldry and Mejias (2019), the ongoing architecture of the global digital economy reproduces colonial patterns of extraction, with data extractivism from poorer countries enriching the Global North. Hence, for BRICS+ countries the risk of living in a world with AI without sovereignty is strategically economic with the declaration focusing on the development of sovereign artificial intelligence models not only as a group agenda but also as individuals, responding directly as an institution to the explorative dynamics. From this perspective, Lee (2024) approach on a transformative leapfrogging process for latecomers countries is a pathway to be built and explored with consciousness and cooperation, focusing for example, on the construction not consumption of AI systems and their capacities rooted in local data, culture, problems and solutions.

Conclusions

his paper argued that artificial leapfrogging is a viable alternative to conventional industrial development for BRICS+ members, but with conditions. What this paper pointed out is that the urge to a new site of industrial development is a necessity for the present, a secure spot for the future and a reparative form to the past of those countries who got too late to industrialism due to external exploitation. The dynamics of data extractivism remind us that without sovereign AI capacity, there are risks of reproducing dependency under a new technological form, precisely what the 2025 BRICS+ Statement seeks to prevent and what Lee (2024) discuss about being the path offered by the transformative leapfrogging route.

There is, though, caution regarding how such countries can act on such panorama. For Rodrik (2016), for members whose labour-absorbing industrialization remains incomplete, a set of AI-driven changes present the risk and the danger of deepening such disparities that cannot be dissolved on their own. With that being said, the outcome for the Global South will not be determined only by the technology itself, but by the quality and speed of BRICS+ political bodies, being them their governments, local institutions and scholars that will have to be at the center of the changing years immediately ahead of us.

Bibliographical References

BAUMEISTER, Roy F.; LEARY, Mark R. Writing narrative literature reviews. *Review of General Psychology*, Washington, v. 1, n. 3, p. 311-320, 1997.

BRICS. *Beijing Declaration*. Beijing: BRICS Chinese Presidency, 2022.

BRICS. *BRICS Leaders Statement on the Global Governance of Artificial Intelligence*. Rio de Janeiro: Brazilian BRICS Presidency, 2025.

BRICS. Joint declaration of the 9th BRICS Industry Ministers' Meeting. Brasília: Brazilian BRICS Presidency, 21 May 2025.

BRICS. MDIC e MEMP integram o Grupo Consultivo do PartNIR, que iniciou debates sobre interesses comuns no contexto da Nova Revolução Industrial. Brasília: Presidência Brasileira do BRICS, 21 Mar. 2025. Available at: <https://brics.br/pt-br/noticias/mdic-e-memp-integram-o-grupo-consultivo-do-partnir-que-iniciou-debates-sobre-interesses-comuns-no-contexto-da-nova-revolucao-industrial>. Accessed on: 10 Mar. 2026.

COULDRY, Nick; MEJIAS, Ulises A. *The costs of connection: how data is colonizing human life and appropriating it for capitalism*. Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2019.

FONG, M. W. L. Technology leapfrogging for developing countries. In: KHOSROW-POUR, Mehdi (ed.). *Encyclopedia of information science and technology*. 2nd ed. Hershey: IGI Global, 2009.

GERSCHENKRON, Alexander. *Economic backwardness in historical perspective: a book of essays*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1962.

LEE, Keun. *Innovation-development detours for latecomers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2024.

LEE, Keun; MALERBA, Franco. Catch-up cycles and changes in industrial leadership: windows of opportunity and responses of firms and countries in the evolution of sectoral systems. *Research Policy*, Amsterdam, v. 46, n. 2, p. 338-351, 2017.

PREBISCH, Raúl. *The economic development of Latin America and its principal problems*. New York: United Nations, 1950.

ROBERTS, Huw et al. *The Chinese room: dominance of China-backed AI standards and governance bodies*. Oxford: Oxford Internet Institute, 2021.

RODRIK, Dani. Premature deindustrialization. *Journal of Economic Growth*, New York, v. 21, n. 1, p. 1–33, 2016.

SANTIAGO, Fernando. *Industry 4.0 and the BRICS economies*. Vienna: United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), 2020. (UNIDO Working Paper).

STEINMUELLER, W. Edward. ICTs and the possibilities for leapfrogging by developing countries. *International Labour Review*, Geneva, v. 140, n. 2, p. 193–210, 2001.

WHITFIELD, Lindsay; WUTTKE, Tobias. Opportunities for latecomer technological catch-up in the era of renewables capitalism: possible pathways out of the periphery. *Development and Change*, Oxford, v. 56, n. 4–5, p. 783–810, 2025.